

Education Quarterly Reviews

Karatas, I., & Oktem, T. (2022). Investigation of the Relationships between Self-Confidence Levels and Job Finding Anxiety of Faculty of Sports Sciences Students. *Education Quarterly Reviews*, 5(1), 291-298.

ISSN 2621-5799

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1993.05.01.440

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Education Quarterly Reviews* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Education Quarterly Reviews* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of education, linguistics, literature, educational theory, research, and methodologies, curriculum, elementary and secondary education, higher education, foreign language education, teaching and learning, teacher education, education of special groups, and other fields of study related to education. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Education Quarterly Reviews* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of education.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

Investigation of the Relationships between Self-Confidence Levels and Job Finding Anxiety of Faculty of Sports Sciences Students

Ismail Karatas¹, Tuncay Oktem²

^{1,2} Faculty of Sports Sciences, The University of Bayburt, Bayburt, Turkey

Correspondence: Ismail Karatas, Faculty of Sports Sciences, The University of Bayburt, Bayburt, Turkey.
E-mail: ismailkrts34@gmail.com

Abstract

In this study, it was aimed to investigate the relationship between the self-confidence levels and job finding anxiety of the students of the faculty of sports sciences within the framework of Bayburt University. In this context, the relational survey model, which is consistent with the main purpose, was used in this quantitative study. The sample of the study consists of a total of 311 students, 113 females and 198 males, at the Faculty of Sports Sciences of Bayburt University. Convenience sampling method, one of the non-probabilistic sampling approaches, was used in the selection of the sample. Questionnaire form was used as data collection tool and this form consists of three parts. In the first part of the questionnaire form includes "Personal Information Form," in the second part includes "Self-Confidence Scale" and in the third part includes "Sports Sciences Students' Job Finding Anxiety Scale." First of all, descriptive statistics were calculated by considering the data type of the raw data obtained through this form. Then, the reliability of the dimensions of the scales related to the data obtained were investigated, and difference and correlation tests were used in statistical evaluations. In this direction, significant differences were determined in terms of the variables of gender, department, grade and place of residence. In addition, it was observed that there were significant correlations within the scope of the age and monthly average family income level of the participants regarding the scales. On the other hand, no significant correlation was found between the monthly average personal income level and the dimensions of the scales. As a result, it was found that there was a negative and significant correlation between the external self-confidence mean scores and job finding anxiety mean scores of the participants. However, no significant correlation was found between the participants' inner self-confidence mean scores and their job finding anxiety mean scores.

Keywords: Student, Self-Confidence, Job Finding Anxiety

1. Introduction

It is claimed that self-confidence is one of the important psychological constructs that has been the subject of many studies recently and affects the academic performance of students (Akin, 2007). Also self-confidence; conceptualized as perceived efficacy (Harter, 1982; Nicholls, 1984) and self-efficacy (Bandura, 1977; 1997). In this context, the concept of self-confidence is the belief that the individual will successfully perform a certain

activity rather than being a general feature, and the individual's confidence in her/his own judgment, ability, power and decisions (Feltz, 1988). In addition, it is stated that the concepts of self-confidence and self-efficacy are used interchangeably in the literature (Akin, 2007). However, some researchers have argued that although self-confidence and self-efficacy are different concepts, they are conceptually close to each other and self-efficacy is domain-specific, while self-confidence can be domain-specific or general (Bandura, 1997; Grundy, 1993; Shrauger & Schohn, 1995). It has been stated that self-confidence can be another aspect of personal efficacy and may emerge as a result of products, unlike self-efficacy (Akin, 2007). However, Feltz (1988) defined self-confidence as similar to the concept of self-efficacy put forward by Bandura (1977). The theory of self-efficacy, which was developed in the social-cognitive context, has been used as a theoretical basis in self-confidence researches generally carried out in various fields (Akin, 2007). According to Bandura's (1982) social cognitive theory, it is claimed to help with recurrence that an individual's self-efficacy and self-confidence stems from his ability to demonstrate a particular ability or behavior, from observing the behavior of others, from verbal feedback, and from being aware of emotions, and such self-confidence results from one's related behavior. In addition, the defining characteristics of self-confidence include belief in positive achievements, perseverance and self-awareness (White, 2009). On the other hand, there is a negative relationship between self-confidence and anxiety (White, 2014).

It has been shown in the literature that low health as a result of mental disorder may be associated with high unemployment (Leino-Arjas et al., 1999; Claussen, 1999; Goldberg et al., 2001; Thomas, Benzeval, & Stansfeld, 2005; Chatterji et al., 2007; Heponiemi et al., 2007; Zhang, Zhao, & Harris, 2009). Especially in periods when the economy is problematic, people with mental illness may be the most disadvantaged in terms of unemployment and financial insecurity (Viinamaki et al., 2000; Evans-Lacko et al., 2013; Knapp & Wong, 2020). Within this framework, unemployment among university graduates is a worldwide problem (Mandyoli, Iwu, & Nxopo, 2017). In this context, the sports sector, which has a very important place in the general economy in terms of its economic volume and wide job opportunities in Turkey and in the world, is also affected by the negative conditions in the labor market (Aslan & Uğraş, 2021). It is stated that it has a direct relationship with sectors such as media, tourism, education, textile, entertainment, health and wellness; It has an indirect relationship with sectors such as electronics, automotive, construction trade, yachting and landscaping and creates employment on a large scale of the sports sector (Mumcu, Karakullukçu, & Karakuş, 2019). In addition, it is claimed that sport helps physical development only on an individual basis and is a concept that is associated with many sectors such as participation, lifelong learning, employment and education (Eruzun, Kınalı, & Erturan Öğüt, 2017). However, it is stated that the employment problems of individuals who graduated from the field of sports sciences will cause anxiety for the future in these individuals (Araç Ilgar & Cihan, 2019). Therefore, unemployment, beyond its harmful economic dimensions, can create a painful and harmful experience, a threat to psychological well-being, and a traumatic situation (Carroll, 2007; Spera, Buhrfeind, & Pennebaker, 1994; Waters & Moore, 2002a).

When the explanations are evaluated from a holistic perspective, unemployment; it is seen as an important source of risk for individuals and families (Clark & Oswald, 1994; Fryer & Fagan, 2003; Hanisch, 1999; Komarovsky, 2004). In this direction, it is considered important to have information about the job finding anxieties and self-confidence of the students of the faculty of sports sciences by considering various variables. In this context, when the relevant literature is examined, it has been seen that there is no study to examine the job finding anxiety of sports science students in terms of various variables. Although, it is seen that there are many studies investigating the self-confidence levels of university students (see Sarıçam & Güven, 2012; Uçar & Duy, 2013; Ödemiş, 2014; Yalınzoğlu Çaka et al., 2017; Doğru, 2017; Süzer, 2020), no study has been found that deals with self-confidence and job finding anxiety together within the framework of sports sciences students. Therefore, it is thought that the results of the research will contribute to the relevant literature, and it is aimed to investigate of the relationships between self-confidence levels and job finding anxiety of faculty of sports sciences students.

2. Method

In this part of the study, the research model, population and sample, data collection tools and data analysis are explained under separate headings.

2.1 Research Model

Survey studies generally aim to describe the current situation related to the subject of the research by photographing (Büyüköztürk et al., 2020). In addition, those who conduct survey research are generally interested in how the characteristics and opinions are distributed within the scope of the participants in the sample, rather than why they originate (Fraenkel & Wallen, 2006). In this context, the relational survey model, which is consistent with the main purpose, was used in this quantitative study.

2.2 Population and Sample

The population of the research consists of 781 students at Bayburt University Faculty of Sports Sciences in the Fall Semester of the 2021-2022 Academic Year. In this framework, a total of 311 students (113 females and 198 males) constitute the sample of the research. Convenience sampling method, which is one of the non-probabilistic sampling approaches, was used in the creation of the sample. In this context, it is understood that the acceptable sample size for the research population has been reached (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016).

2.3 Data Collection Tools

The questionnaire form, which was prepared in accordance with the aims of the research, was applied to the participants in the population, on a voluntary basis, for about two weeks in the Fall Semester of the 2021-2022 Academic Year. During the implementation of the data collection tools, necessary explanations were given to the participants and it was ensured that they answered the questionnaire correctly. In the first part of the questionnaire form includes "Personal Information Form," in the second part includes "Self-Confidence Scale" and in the third part includes "Sports Sciences Students' Job Finding Anxiety Scale."

2.3.1 Personal Information Form

In the Personal Information Form, there are statements about obtaining the participants' gender, age, department, grade, place of residence, monthly average personal income level and monthly average family income level (including personal income).

2.3.2 Self-Confidence Scale

"Self-Confidence Scale" was developed by Akın (2007) to determine students' self-confidence levels. Data regarding the development process of the scale were obtained from 796 high school students from various high schools. The scale consists of 33 items and is in five-point Likert type. In addition, this scale; It consists of two sub-dimensions, inner self-confidence and external self-confidence. The construct and concurrent validity of the scale were examined as validity studies. In order to determine the factor structure and subscales of the scale, exploratory and confirmatory factor analyzes were performed. The short form of the Coopersmith Self-Esteem Inventory, developed by Coopersmith (1967) and adapted into Turkish by Pişkin (1997), and the Self-Confidence Scale were applied to the participants simultaneously in order to examine the concurrent validity of the scale. Internal consistency and test-retest reliability coefficients were examined for reliability studies, and corrected item-total correlations were examined for item analysis. The internal consistency coefficients of the Self-Confidence Scale were found to be 0.83 and 0.85 for the inner self-confidence and external self-confidence subscales, respectively. The test-retest reliability coefficients of the scale were found to be 0.97 for the inner self-confidence and 0.87 for the external self-confidence. It was observed that the item-total correlations of the scale ranged from 0.30 to 0.72. In this context, it was concluded that the Self-Confidence Scale is a valid and reliable measurement tool that can be used in the fields of education and psychology (Akın, 2007). Although the scale was developed on high school students, it was concluded that the scale items could also be applied to university students after the examinations of five academicians who are experts in the relevant field. In addition, there are many studies in the relevant literature in which the scale was applied to university students (see Sariçam & Güven, 2012; Uçar & Duy, 2013; Ödemiş, 2014; Yalınzoğlu Çaka et al., 2017; Doğru, 2017; Süzer, 2020).

2.3.3 Sports Sciences Students' Job Finding Anxiety Scale

“Sports Sciences Students' Job Finding Anxiety Scale” was developed by Aslan and Uğraş (2021) in order to determine the job finding anxiety of sports sciences students. Data on the development process of the scale were obtained from a total of 525 university students studying in sports sciences. The scale consists of eight items and is in five-point Likert type. In addition, this scale consists of one dimension. In the scale development study, exploratory sequential design, one of the mixed research methods, was applied. Thematic analysis method was used for the analysis of qualitative data. Exploratory factor was used for the compatibility of the items obtained as a result of this analysis to the scale, and confirmatory factor analysis was applied to test this structure. In addition, the internal consistency coefficient (Cronbach's Alpha) of the scale was calculated as 0.958. As a result, it has been determined that the scale is a valid and reliable measurement tool (Aslan & Uğraş, 2021).

2.4 Analysis of Data

IBM SPSS version 23.0 was used in the analysis of the data. First of all, descriptive statistics were calculated by considering the data type of the raw data in the scale form obtained and transferred to the program. Then, t-Test and One-Way ANOVA were used for difference tests, Pearson's Correlation and Spearman's Rank-Order Correlation analyzes were used for correlation tests in statistical evaluations according to whether the data obtained showed normal distribution or not. In this context, Hochberg's GT2 and Games-Howell post-hoc tests were applied for One-Way ANOVA, considering the homogeneity assumption and the distribution of the participants between groups. In calculating the reliability of the scales, Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was taken into account within the framework of internal consistency. In addition, the level of significance was determined as 0.05 in statistical evaluations.

3. Results

In this part of the study, the findings obtained as a result of the analysis of the relevant data were presented and interpreted in the form of tables.

Table 1: Frequency and Percentages of Variables

Variable	Group	f	%
Gender	Female	113	36,3
	Male	198	63,7
Department	Coaching Education	122	39,2
	Physical Education and Sports Teaching	94	30,2
	Sports Management	95	30,5
Grade	1st Grade	97	31,2
	2nd Grade	72	23,2
	3rd Grade	88	28,3
	4th Grade	54	17,4
Place of Residence	Village + Town + Community	56	18,0
	County Seat	146	46,9
	City Center	109	35,0
Total		311	100,0

When Table 1 is examined, it is seen that the number of male regarding the participants is approximately 1.75 times the number of females, and the department with the highest number of participants is coaching education. In addition, it is understood that the first grade has the highest number of participants and the fourth grade has the lowest number of participants. In addition, it is seen that the majority of the participants reside in the county seat.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Age, Average Monthly Personal Income Level, and Average Monthly Family Income Level Variables

Variable	n	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum	Skewness	Kurtosis
Age	310	20,81	21,00	2,207	17	36	1,930	8,611
Average Monthly Personal Income Level	310	799,5968	650,0000	1047,41642	,00	7500,00	2,730	9,639
Average Monthly Family Income Level (Including Personal Income)	291	3643.55	3000.00	2753.456	500	25000	2.960	14.900

When Table 2 is examined, the mean of age variable of the participants is 20.81 and the standard deviation is 2.207; Average monthly personal income level variable in Turkish Lira type is 799,5968 and standard deviation is 1047,41642; It is seen that the average monthly family income level (including personal income) variable in Turkish Lira type is 3643.55 and its standard deviation is 2753.456. In addition, when the skewness and kurtosis values of the variables were examined, it was concluded that these variables did not exhibit normal distribution (see George & Mallery, 2010; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013).

Table 3: Reliability Analysis Results of Scales

Dimensions	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
Inner Self-confidence	,873	17
External Self-confidence	,860	16
Job Finding Anxiety	,925	8

When Table 3 is examined, it is seen that the internal consistency coefficients (Cronbach's Alpha) calculated within the scope of the research and the sub-dimensions of the job finding anxiety scale ($\alpha=0.925$) and the inner self-confidence ($\alpha=0.873$) and external self-confidence ($\alpha=0.860$) subscales in the context of the self-confidence scale are examined. appear to be highly reliable.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics of Scales

Dimensions	n	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum	Skewness	Kurtosis
Inner Self-confidence	311	4,1874	4,2941	,53550	1,59	5,00	-1,072	1,572
External Self-confidence	311	4,0870	4,1875	,56176	1,69	5,00	-,977	1,306
Job Finding Anxiety	311	3,4136	3,5000	1,07037	1,00	5,00	-,405	-,587

When Table 4 is examined, the mean score of the inner self-confidence subscale is 4.1874 and the standard deviation is 0.53550, and the mean score of the external self-confidence subscale is 4.0870 and the standard deviation is 0.56176. In addition, it was found that the mean score of the job finding anxiety scale was 3.4136 and the standard deviation was 1.07037. In this context, within the framework of self-confidence, it can be said that the inner self-confidence and external self-confidence levels of the participants are at a high level, and their job finding anxiety is at a moderate level. In addition, it was accepted that these variables exhibited normal distribution within the framework of skewness and kurtosis values (see George & Mallery, 2010; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013).

Table 5: Results of Spearman's Rank-Order Correlation Analysis Between Scales and Age, Personal Income Level and Family Income Level Variables

Variables	Inner Self-confidence	External Self-confidence	Job Finding Anxiety
Age	r	,201*	,140*
	p	,000	,014
	n	310	310
Average Monthly Personal Income Level	r	,009	,061
	p	,878	,286

	n	310	310	310
Average Monthly Family Income	r	-,032	,013	-,188*
Level (Including Personal Income)	p	,592	,830	,001
	n	291	291	291

*p<0.05

According to Table 5, it was found that there were positive and low level statistically significant correlations between the age variable and the mean scores of the subscales of inner self-confidence ($r=0.201$; $p<0.05$) and external self-confidence ($r=0.140$; $p<0.05$). In addition, it was found that there was a negative and low level statistically significant correlation between the mean score of the job finding anxiety scale and the average monthly family income variable ($r=-0.188$; $p<0.05$). However, no statistically significant correlation was found for other conditions related to the variables ($p>0.05$).

Table 6: Results of t-Test by Gender Variable

Dimensions	Gender	n	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	t	p
Inner Self-confidence	Female	113	4,1255	,54932	309	-1,546	,123
	Male	198	4,2228	,52558			
External Self-confidence	Female	113	4,0669	,56570	309	-,476	,634
	Male	198	4,0985	,56062			
Job Finding Anxiety	Female	113	3,6383	1,07741	309	2,828*	,005
	Male	198	3,2854	1,04757			

*p<0.05

When Table 6 is examined, it is seen that there is a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the participants' job finding anxiety in the context of the gender variable ($t_{(309)}=2.828$; $p<0.05$). In addition, this significant difference was found to be in favor of females. However, no statistically significant difference was found for other conditions related to the gender variable ($p>0.05$).

Table 7: Results of ANOVA by Department Variable

Dimensions	Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	F	p	Significant Difference
Inner Self-confidence	Coaching Education (1)	4,1958	,58205	310	,061	,941	---
	Physical Education and Sports Teaching (2)	4,1927	,49916				
	Sports Management (3)	4,1715	,51257				
External Self-confidence	Coaching Education (1)	4,1009	,59366	310	,106	,899	---
	Physical Education and Sports Teaching (2)	4,0904	,52376				
	Sports Management (3)	4,0658	,56120				
Job Finding Anxiety	Coaching Education (1)	3,6363	1,00746	310	7,610*	,001	1>3 2>3
	Physical Education and Sports Teaching (2)	3,4601	1,01637				
	Sports Management (3)	3,0816	1,12777				

*p<0.05

When Table 7 is examined, it is seen that there is a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the participants' job finding anxiety in the context of the department variable ($F_{(2-308)}=7.610$; $p<0.05$). In addition, this significant difference between coaching education and sports management departments; between the physical education and sports teaching and sports management departments, and it was seen that both differences were against the sports management department. However, no statistically significant difference was found for other conditions related to the department variable ($p>0.05$).

Table 8: Results of ANOVA by Grade Variable

Dimensions	Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	F	p	Significant Difference
Inner Self-confidence	1st Grade	4,1771	,51516	310	3,104*	,027	4th Grade>2nd Grade
	2nd Grade	4,0572	,48134				
	3rd Grade	4,2086	,61675				
	4th Grade	4,3453	,46092				
	1st Grade	4,1521	,48822	310	2,369	,071	---

External Self-confidence	2nd Grade	3,9635	,57030	310	7,468*	,000	4th Grade>1st Grade 4th Grade>2nd Grade 3rd Grade>2nd Grade
	3rd Grade	4,0518	,63535				
	4th Grade	4,1921	,52346				
Job Finding Anxiety	1st Grade	3,2745	,98733	310	7,468*	,000	4th Grade>1st Grade 4th Grade>2nd Grade 3rd Grade>2nd Grade
	2nd Grade	3,0781	1,11180				
	3rd Grade	3,5440	1,08676				
	4th Grade	3,8981	,94078				

*p<0.05

When Table 8 is examined, it is seen that there is a statistically significant difference between the inner self-confidence mean scores of the participants in the context of the grade variable ($F_{(3-307)}=3.104$; $p<0.05$). This significant difference was between the second grade and fourth grade groups, and it was seen that the difference was in favor of the fourth grade group. In addition, it was determined that there was a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of job finding anxiety ($F_{(3-307)}=7,468$; $p<0.05$). This significant difference is between first grade and fourth grade, second grade and fourth grade groups, and both of the differences are in favor of the fourth grade group; It was found that the difference was in favor of the third grade group, between the second grade and third grade groups. However, no statistically significant difference was found for other conditions related to the grade variable ($p>0.05$).

Table 9: Results of ANOVA by Place of Residence Variable

Dimensions	Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	F	p	Significant Difference
Inner Self-confidence	Village + Town + Community (1)	3,9926	,68655	310	4,768*	,009	2>1
	County Seat (2)	4,2454	,49309				
	City Center (3)	4,2099	,48158				
External Self-confidence	Village + Town + Community (1)	3,8125	,69157	310	8,561*	,000	3>1 2>1
	County Seat (2)	4,1511	,50401				
	City Center (3)	4,1422	,52297				
Job Finding Anxiety	Village + Town + Community (1)	3,4375	1,08972	310	,883	,415	---
	County Seat (2)	3,4846	1,06146				
	City Center (3)	3,3062	1,07347				

*p<0.05

When Table 9 is examined, it is seen that there is a statistically significant difference between the inner self-confidence mean scores of the participants in the context of the place of residence variable ($F_{(2-308)}=4.768$; $p<0.05$). This significant difference is between the village+town+community and county seat groups, and it was seen that the difference was in favor of the county seat group. In addition, it was determined that there was a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of external self-confidence ($F_{(2-308)}=8.561$; $p<0.05$). This significant difference was between village+town+community and county seat and village+town+community and city center groups, and the differences were found to be in favor of county seat and city center groups. However, no statistically significant difference was found between the mean scores of job finding anxiety in the context of the place of residence variable ($p>0.05$).

Table 10: Results of Pearson's Correlation Analysis Between Self-Confidence and Job Finding Anxiety

Variables	Inner Self-confidence	External Self-confidence
Job Finding Anxiety	r	-,050
	p	,377
	n	311

*p<0.05

When Table 10 is examined, it is seen that there is a negative and low level statistically significant correlation between the external self-confidence mean scores of the participants and their job finding anxiety mean scores ($r=-0.116$; $p<0.05$). Therefore, it can be concluded that as the external self-confidence levels of the participants increase, their job finding anxiety levels will decrease. On the other hand, there was no statistically significant correlation between the participants' inner self-confidence mean scores and their job finding anxiety mean scores ($p>0.05$).

4. Discussion and Conclusion

In this study, it was aimed to investigate the relationship between the self-confidence levels and job finding anxiety of the students of the faculty of sports sciences within the framework of Bayburt University. In this context, a questionnaire form was prepared in accordance with the purpose of the research, and the raw data obtained as a result of the application of this form to the research group were converted into findings using various statistical analysis techniques. In this context, the results obtained based on the findings were discussed within the framework of the relevant literature and the research was detailed. In this direction, it can be said that the inner self-confidence and external self-confidence of the participants within the framework of self-confidence are at a high level, and their job finding anxiety is at a moderate level.

Considering the gender variable, it has been determined that females have a higher level of job finding anxiety than males. In the study conducted by Tekin Tayfun and Korkmaz (2016), it was found that the general unemployment anxiety scores of female university students were higher than the general unemployment anxiety scores of male university students. On the other hand, in the study conducted by Karşlı (2021) on the anxiety of finding a job in theology faculty students, it was determined that the unemployment anxiety of males was significantly higher than that of females. In the study conducted by Yasar and Turgut (2020), it was determined that although there was no statistically significant difference in the total mean score of unemployment anxiety of female and male participants, the unemployment anxiety of male participants was higher than that of female participants. Yumuşaker (2020) found that there was no significant difference between the gender of accounting students at the associate degree level and their anxiety about finding a job. However, it is stated that gender is an important factor in the response to unemployment (Waters & Moore, 2002b). In this context, it can be thought that the fact that females have different thoughts than males in the face of a situation is effective in increasing the future anxiety of female university students (Karagün & Çolak, 2009). Therefore, it is thought that the result reached within the scope of the gender variable for this study is probable.

Considering the age variable, it was found that as the age of the participants increased, both inner self-confidence and external self-confidence levels increased. This result is partially consistent with some studies in the literature (Öztürk Karataş, 2017; Albayrak et al., 2020). Depending on age, individuals can express their emotions in a more controlled and appropriate way. It also occurs in behavioral maturation with age. Therefore, it can be argued that these situations are effective variables at the level of self-confidence. In this context, it is thought that the results obtained within the scope of the age variable are probable.

Considering the department variable, it has been determined that the level of job finding anxiety of the students of coaching education and physical education and sports teaching departments is higher than that of sports management students. When the opinions of the students of the sports management department about the future anxieties related to the study conducted by Araç İlgar and Cihan (2019), were examined, it was determined that half of the participants in the study had professional future anxiety. On the other hand, it can be said that the students of the sports management department have the opportunity to become a teacher and a coach, which enables them to look to the future with more hope than the students of the coaching education and physical education and sports teaching departments, and in this context, the scores of job finding anxiety are lower.

Considering the grade variable, it is seen that the third grade students have higher job finding anxiety than the second grade students and the fourth grade students have higher job finding anxiety than students in the first and second grades. In addition, it was determined that the fourth grade students had higher inner self-confidence levels than the second grade students. However, in the study conducted by Öztürk Karataş (2017) on students of physical education and sports school, it was determined that the self-confidence scores of the participants did not differ according to the grade level. However, in the study conducted by Karşlı (2021), it was determined that the unemployment anxiety levels of those studying in the upper grades (such as the 3rd and 4th grades) were significantly higher than those of the lower grades. In the study conducted by Ersoy Kart and Erdost (2008), it was determined that the anxiety levels of the students increase as the graduation stage approaches. Turgut, Gökyürek and Yenel (2004) in the study of physical education and sports school students; It was concluded that 72.3% of them expressed "Yes" in post-graduation unemployment anxiety and they were very worried about unemployment.

Also, Demir and Taşkıran (2018) determined in their study that senior students had lower hopes of finding a job than students from other grades. Although there is a widespread belief that an increase in the level of education will bring a job guarantee (Kıdır, 2017), the educated workforce is also heavily and directly affected by unemployment, and these social realities cause students to worry about being unemployed while they continue their education (Kıdır, 2010). In line with this information, it can be said that the situation of not being able to find a job in the post-graduation period with the increase in the grade level affects the individuals negatively and causes them to experience unemployment anxiety.

Considering the variable of place of residence, it was determined that the participants living in the county seat had higher inner and external self-confidence levels compared to those living in the village+town+community, and the external self-confidence levels of the participants living in the city center were higher than those living in the village+town+community. Karademir (2015) determined that the participants living in the province and county have more self-confidence. In the study conducted by Yağan (2019), it was determined that the participants living in the metropolitan city had a higher self-confidence than the participants living in the village/town. On the other hand, in the study conducted by Musa (2020), no difference was found between self-confidence and place of residence. However, it can be said that individuals living in areas with high population may have higher self-confidence than those living in areas with low population. It can be said that self-confidence is quite effective for individuals living in densely populated areas to make themselves visible in crowds.

Considering the family income variable, it was determined that as the family income increased, the job finding anxiety decreased. In this context, some characteristics of students (gender, socio-economic level of the family, personality, parental profession, school success, place of residence and friend circle) are the factors that cause anxiety (Çakmak & Hevedanlı, 2004). The city where the students study in university life, their socio-economic levels, relations in the school environment, etc. many factors affect their anxiety (Dursun & Aytaç, 2009). It is also stated that as the income level of the family increases, the hope of finding a job suitable for the qualifications of the individuals increases (Mütevelliöğlu et al., 2010). Based on this information, it can be said that the increase in the income level of the households has positive effects on the anxiety of finding a job and reduces the anxiety levels of the individuals.

When the research is considered in the context of the relationship between self-confidence and job finding anxiety, it was found that as external self-confidence increases, job finding anxiety decreases. Anxiety; It is known that it means fear and worry (Köknel, 1987) and anxiety causes worry, tension and fear (Karageorghis & Terry, 2010). Bandura (1997) self-confidence; It is defined as the individual's confidence in his own abilities, judgment, power and decisions, and the belief that he can achieve a certain activity. In addition, the concept of self-confidence is divided into inner and external self-confidence. While inner self-confidence is related to individuals' self-confidence, external self-confidence is a situation related to individuals' self-confidence regarding their lives in the external environment and social environment (Akın, 2007). In this context, external self-confidence; easy communication, expressing oneself in a healthy way, controlling emotions and taking risks (Akın, 2007). In this respect, communication skill is expressed as "the ability to convey one's feelings, thoughts, beliefs and attitudes in an understandable and purposeful way" (Tiryaki Şen et al., 2013). Being able to control one's emotions can be defined as managing these emotions instead of being under the control of one's own desires and requests. In this context, it is thought that individuals who have high communication skills and can control their emotions can express themselves effectively. In line with this information, it is thought that individuals with high external self-confidence express themselves effectively and keep their emotions under control. Therefore, it can be said that these situations reduce their anxiety about finding a job and keep individuals away from negative thoughts about the future.

As a result, making plans to increase the external self-confidence levels of students in sports sciences may reduce their job finding anxiety. Accordingly, it is thought that the negativities arising from the job finding anxiety can be reduced. In addition, new information that will contribute to the literature has been obtained with the research findings. However, the results of the analysis include limited number of participant data considering the research group. For this reason, similar studies can be conducted with a large data set to cover all age groups. In addition, research results can be diversified by conducting qualitative, mixed and/or experimental studies on a research

group with similar characteristics. In this context, different results can be reached that will contribute to the literature.

References

- Akın, A. (2007). The development and psychometric characteristics of the self-confidence scale. *Abant İzzet Baysal University Journal of Faculty of Education*, 7(2), 167-176.
- Albayrak, V., Kızılkoca, M., & Özcan, E. (2020). The investigation of first grade student's self-confidence levels who has sports education: Sample of Fırat University. *Journal of History School*, 47, 2853-2861.
- Araç Ilgar, E., & Cihan, B. B. (2019). Examination of sectoral expectations, professional uncertainty and future anxiety of students of sports management programs: A phenomenological analysis. *Journal of Sports Education*, 3(1), 81-92.
- Aslan, M., & Uğraş, S. (2021). Validity and reliability study of the sports sciences students' job finding anxiety scale. *International Journal of Eurasian Education and Culture*, 6(13), 1143-1170.
- Bandura, A. (1977). Self-efficacy: Toward an unifying theory of behavioral change. *Psychological Review*, 84, 191-215.
- Bandura, A. (1982). Self-efficacy mechanism in human agency. *American Psychologist*, 37(2), 122-147.
- Bandura, A. (1997). *Self-efficacy: The Exercise of Control*. New York: Freeman.
- Büyüköztürk, Ş., Çakmak, E. K., Akgün, Ö. E., Karadeniz, Ş., & Demirel, F. (2020). *Eğitimde Bilimsel Araştırma Yöntemleri* (29. Edt.). Ankara: Pegem Akademi.
- Carroll, N. (2007). Unemployment and psychological well-being. *The Economic Record*, 83(262), 287-302.
- Chatterji, P., Alegria, M., Lu, M., & Takeuchi, D. (2007). Psychiatric disorders and labor market outcomes: Evidence from the National Latino and Asian American study. *Health Economics*, 16(10), 1069-1090.
- Clark, A., & Oswald, A. (1994). Unhappiness and unemployment. *Economic Journal, Royal Economic Society*, 104, 648-659.
- Claussen, B. (1999). Health and re-employment in a five-year follow-up of long-term unemployed. *Scandinavian Journal of Public Health*, 27(2), 94-100.
- Coopersmith, S. (1967). *The Antecedents of Self-Esteem*. New York: Freeman.
- Çakmak, Ö., & Hevedanlı, M. (2004). Biyoloji öğretmen adaylarının kaygılarını etkileyen etmenler. *XIII. Ulusal Eğitim Bilimleri Kurultayı*, 06-09 July 2004, Malatya-Turkey.
- Demir, Ö., & Taşkıran, G. (2018). A quantitative research on the factors affecting the fea candidates' hopes of finding job. *Journal of Labour Relations*, 9(1), 42-57.
- Doğru, Z. (2017). Evaluation of self-confidence and self-efficacy perception levels of physical education and sport education department students. *Journal of Physical Education and Sports Studies*, 9(1), 13-23.
- Dursun, S., & Aytac, S. (2009). Üniversite öğrencileri arasında işsizlik kaygısı. *Uludağ Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 28(1), 71-84.
- Ersoy Kart, M., & Erdost, H. E. (2008). Unemployment worries among Turkish university students. *Social Behavior and Personality: An international journal*, 36(2), 275-288.
- Eruzun, C., Kınalı, Y., & Erturan Öğüt, E. E. (2017). A qualitative view into the employment problems of sports management graduates in Turkey. *International Journal of Recreation and Sports Science*, 1(1), 13-21.
- Evans-Lacko, S., Knapp, M., McCrone, P., Thornicroft, G., & Mojtabai, R. (2013). The mental health consequences of the recession: Economic hardship and employment of people with mental health problems in 27 European countries. *PloS One*, 8(7), e69792.
- Feltz, D. L. (1988). Self-confidence and sports performance. *Exercise and Sports Science Reviews*, 16, 423-458.
- Fraenkel, J. R., & Wallen, N. E. (2006). *How to Design and Evaluate Research in Education* (6th ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill International Edition.
- Fryer, D., & Fagan, R. (2003). Towards a community psychological perspective on unemployment and mental health research. *American Journal of Community Psychology*, 32(1/2), 89-96.
- George, D., & Mallery, P. (2010). *SPSS for Windows Step by Step. A Simple Study Guide and Reference*. Boston, MA: Pearson Education, Inc, 10.
- Goldberg, R. W., Lucksted, A., McNary, S., Gold, J. M., Dixon, L., & Lehman, A. (2001). Correlates of long-term unemployment among inner-city adults with serious and persistent mental illness. *Psychiatric Services*, 52(1), 101-103.
- Grundy, S. E. (1993). The confidence scale and psychometric characteristics. *Nurse Educator*, 18(1), 6-9.

- Hanisch, K. A. (1999). Job loss and unemployment research from 1994 to 1998: A review and recommendations for research and intervention. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 55, 188-220.
- Harter, S. (1982). The perceived competence scale for children. *Child Development*, 53, 87-97.
- Heponiemi, T., Elovainio, M., Manderbacka, K., Aalto, A. M., Kivimäki, M., & Keskimäki, I. (2007). Relationship between unemployment and health among health care professionals: Health selection or health effect?. *Journal of Psychosomatic Research*, 63(4), 425-431.
- Karademir, N. (2015). Students perception of self-confidence in department of geography in faculty of science and letters. *Kahramanmaraş Sütçü İmam Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 12(1), 53-77.
- Karageorghis, C. I., & Terry, P. C. (2010). *Inside Sport Psychology*. United Kingdom: Human Kinetics.
- Karagün, E., & Çolak, S. (2009). Kpss sınavına hazırlanan beden eğitimi ve spor öğretmenliği bölümü son sınıf öğrencilerinin kaygı düzeylerinin incelenmesi. 6. *Ulusal Beden Eğitimi ve Spor Öğretmenliği Sempozyumu*, June 2009, pp. 350-361.
- Karşlı, N. (2021). Unemployment anxiety and religiousness in the students of the faculty of theology. *The Journal of Gumushane University Faculty of Theology*, 20, 220-249.
- Kıcıır, B. (2010). *Üniversite Son Sınıf Öğrencilerinde İşsizlik Kaygısı: Psikolojik Etmenler Açısından Bir İnceleme*. Master's Thesis, Ankara University, Ankara-Turkey.
- Kıcıır, B. (2017). Educated youth unemployment and unemployment worry. *Çalışma ve Toplum Dergisi*, 54(3), 1369-1396.
- Knapp, M., & Wong, G. (2020). Economics and mental health: The current scenario. *World Psychiatry: Official Journal of the World Psychiatric Association (WPA)*, 19(1), 3-14.
- Komarovsky, M. (2004) *The Unemployed Man and His Family: The Effect of Unemployment upon the Status of the Man in Fifty-Nine Families*. Lanham, MD: Altamira Press.
- Köknel, Ö. (1987). *Zorlanan İnsan*. İstanbul: Altın Kitaplar Yayınevi.
- Leino-Arjas, P., Liira, J., Mutanen, P., Malmivaara, A., & Matikainen, E. (1999). Predictors and consequences of unemployment among construction workers: Prospective cohort study. *BMJ (Clinical research ed.)*, 319, 600-605.
- Mandyoli, B., Iwu, C. G., & Nxopo, Z. (2017). Is there a nexus between social entrepreneurship and the employability of graduates?. *Foundations of Management*, 9(1), 61-74.
- Mumcu, H., Karakullukçu, Ö., & Karakuş, M. (2019). Youth employment in the sports sector. *OPUS International Journal of Society Researches*, 11, 2649-2665.
- Musa, M. (2020). Investigation of social appearance anxiety and self-confidence levels of individuals playing sports in fitness centers according to some variables. *Niğde Ömer Halisdemir University Journal of Physical Education and Sports Sciences*, 14(3), 503-518.
- Mütevellioglu, N., Zambak, M., & Mert, M. (2010). Unemployment, college youth, and future: Inspirations from a field study. *Cumhuriyet University Journal of Economics and Administrative Sciences*, 11(1), 207-229.
- Nicholls, J. G. (1984). Achievement motivation: Conceptions of ability, subjective experience, task choice, and performance. *Psychological Review*, 91(3), 328-346.
- Ödemiş, M. (2014). *Investigation of The Impact of The 12 Weeks Latin Dance Training Course On Self Confidence of University Students*. Master's Thesis, Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart University, Çanakkale-Turkey.
- Öztürk Karataş, E. (2017). *Analysis of Leadership Orientations and Self-Confidence Behaviors of Physical Education and Sports School Students*. Master's Thesis, İnönü University, Malatya-Turkey.
- Pişkin, M. (1997, April). Türk ve İngiliz lise öğrencilerinin benlik saygısı yönünden karşılaştırılması. III. *Ulusal Psikolojik Danışma ve Rehberlik Kongresi*, Adana, Turkey.
- Sarıçam, H., & Güven, M. (2012). Self-confidence and religious attitude. *International Journal of Social Science*, 5(7), 573-586.
- Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2016). *Research Methods for Business: A Skill-Building Approach* (7th Edition). West Sussex: John Wiley & Sons Ltd.
- Shrauger, J. S., & Schohn, M. (1995). Self-confidence in college students: Conceptualization, measurement, and behavioral implications. *Assessment*, 2(3), 255-278.
- Spera, S., Buhrfeind, E., & Penebaker, J. W. (1994). Expressive writing and coping with job loss. *Academy of Management Journal*, 3, 722-733.
- Süzer, M. S. (2020). *The Relationship Between Intercultural Sensitivity and Self-Confidence of University Students: Sample of Çağ University*. Master's Thesis, Çağ University, Mersin-Turkey.
- Tabachnick, B. G., & Fidell, L. S. (2013). *Using Multivariate Statistics* (6th ed.). Boston: Allyn and Bacon.

- Tekin Tayfun, A. N., & Korkmaz, A. (2016). The unemployment anxiety of university students: A research on Süleyman Demirel University students. *Mehmet Akif Ersoy University Journal of Social Sciences Institute*, 8(17), 534-558.
- Thomas, C., Benzeval, M., & Stansfeld, S. A. (2005). Employment transitions and mental health: An analysis from the British household panel survey. *Journal of Epidemiology and Community Health*, 59(3), 243-249.
- Tiryaki Şen, H., Taşkın Yılmaz, F., & Pekşen Ünüvar, Ö. (2013). Levels of comminaciation skills of service education nurses. *Journal of Psychiatric Nursing*, 4(1), 13-20.
- Turgut, M., Gökyürek, B., & Yenel, İ. F. (2004). Determination of the preference causes and expectations of the students having coucation in the areas of trainer education administration and sports management in the schools of physical education and sports. *Ahi Evran University Journal of Kırşehir Education Faculty*, 5(1), 91-99.
- Uçar, T., & Duy, B. (2013). The relationship between locus of control and self-confidence with problem solving skills of midwifery and nursing students. *TAF Preventive Medicine Bulletin*, 12(6), 689-698.
- Viinamaki, H., Hintikka, J., Kontula, O., Niskanen, L., & Koskela, K. (2000). Mental health at population level during an economic recession in Finland. *Nordic Journal of Psychiatry*, 54(3), 177-182.
- Waters, L. E., & Moore, K. A. (2002a). Reducing latent deprivation during unemployment: The role of meaningful leisure activity. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 75, 15-32.
- Waters, L. E., & Moore, K. A. (2002b). Predicting self-esteem during unemployment: The effect of gender, financial deprivation, alternate roles, and social support. *Journal of Employment Counseling*, 39(4), 171-189.
- White, K. A. (2009). Self-confidence: A concept analysis. *Nursing Forum*, 44(2), 103-114.
- White, K. A. (2014). Development and validation of a tool to measure self-confidence and anxiety in nursing students during clinical decision making. *The Journal of Nursing Education*, 53(1), 14-22.
- Yağan, K. (2019). *Scrutiny on the Social Appearance Anxiety and Self-Confidence Levels of the Individuals Attending Fitness Centers*. Master's Thesis, Karamanoğlu Mehmetbey University, Karaman-Turkey.
- Yalınzoğlu Çaka, S., Topal, S., Karakaya Suzan, Ö., Çınar, N., & Altınkaynak, S. (2017). The relationship between nursing students' health perception and self-confidence. *Journal of Human Rhythm*, 3(4), 199-203.
- Yasar, O. M., & Turgut, M. (2020). Unemployment anxiety of last year college students. *Cypriot Journal of Educational Science*, 15(1), 56-64.
- Yumuşaker, M. C. (2020). *The Analysis of Anxiety of Finding a Job and Attitudes Directed to Course of Students Taken Accounting Courses: A Research on the Students of Accounting and Tax Applications Programme*. Master's Thesis, Osmaniye Korkut Ata University, Osmaniye-Turkey.
- Zhang, X., Zhao, X., & Harris, A. (2009). Chronic diseases and labour force participation in Australia. *Journal of Health Economics*, 28(1), 91-108.